

Communication as a way to develop creativity in higher education: Analysis through external internships in business management studies

La comunicación como vía para el desarrollo de la creatividad en la educación superior: Análisis a través de las prácticas externas en gestión de empresas

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The main objective of this study is to analyze employers' perceptions and students' self-perceptions regarding two of the key competencies developed in external internships: creativity and communication skills. It also aims to observe the existence of differences in students' self-perceptions in both competencies according to their gender. **Methodology:** The study population is made up of employers and students participating in the internships for the Degree in Business Administration and Management at the Ourense Campus (University of Vigo). A cross-sectional observational approach using a descriptive correlational design was used to analyze 638 internship reports. **Results:** Both employers and students agree that there is a positive and significant link between the two skills. On the other hand, creativity is not so highly rated, being perceived as lower by the students. No differences were observed in the competencies rated by students or employers according to students' gender. However, regarding the internship duration, the students perceive that it influences the acquisition of competencies. **Discussion y conclusions:** External internships are an ideal complement to university education for the development of competencies. The work environment is key to the development of creativity and innovation, so transferring the implementation of communication skills to a deliberately creative context such as business can contribute to improving students' skills.

Keywords: Communication skills; Creativity; Extracurricular internships; Gender; Duration of internship; University studies; Transversal competencies.

RESUMEN

Introducción: El objetivo principal de este estudio es analizar la percepción de los empleadores y la autopercepción del alumnado para dos de las competencias clave desarrolladas en las prácticas externas: la creatividad y destrezas comunicativas. También se indaga en la existencia de diferencias para ambas competencias en función del género del alumnado y de la duración de las prácticas. **Metodología:** La población objeto de estudio está formada por los empleadores y alumnado participantes en las prácticas del Grado en Administración y Dirección de Empresas del Campus de Ourense (Universidade de Vigo). Se analizan 638 expedientes de prácticas, para lo cual se utiliza un enfoque observacional transversal mediante un diseño descriptivo correlacional. **Resultados:** Se observa la existencia de una correlación positiva y significativa entre las dos competencias, tanto en opinión de los empleadores como del alumnado. Además, cabe destacar la alta valoración de las destrezas comunicativas proporcionadas por ambos colectivos. Por el contrario, la creatividad no es tan altamente valorada, percibiéndola especialmente como más baja el alumnado. No se observan diferencias en ninguna de las competencias valoradas por parte de ambos colectivos en función del género del estudiantado. Sin embargo, el alumnado si percibe que la duración de las prácticas influye en la adquisición de las competencias. **Discusión y Conclusiones:** Las prácticas externas son un complemento idóneo a la formación universitaria para el desarrollo de competencias. El entorno laboral es clave para que se desarrolle la creatividad y la innovación, por lo que trasladar la implementación de las destrezas comunicativas a un contexto deliberadamente creativo como el empresarial puede contribuir a mejorar las habilidades del alumnado.

Palabras clave: Destrezas comunicativas; Creatividad; Prácticas extracurriculares; Género; Duración prácticas; Estudios universitarios; Competencias transversales.

1. Introduction

A crucial aspect that determines the academic quality of universities is to establish a strong connection between the education provided, both at a technical and competence level, and the requirements of an increasingly changing, competitive, and demanding job market. Thus, many faculties try to channel this important relationship through specific strategic plans, which aim to meet these needs and demands to favor the employability of students. In addition to the specific activities that can be developed to intensify the relationships between the university and the company through cycles of conferences, visits to facilities, workshops, or seminars, an important part of university degrees have the possibility of carrying out external internships to put into practice the knowledge and competences acquired, reinforcing the valuable collaboration between the university and the community (Lei and Yin, 2019).

Previous studies have observed that external internships have important benefits for students. On the one hand, it has been highlighted that they constitute a valuable experience that will give students the possibility to observe for themselves the transition between the academic and the work world (Silva et al., 2018). On the other hand, they allow students to improve and acquire certain competencies that are difficult to learn or put into practice in the classroom, such as teamwork, negotiation skills, leadership skills, and oral and written communication competencies (Bayerlein and Jeske, 2018; Urquía-Grande and Pérez-Estébanez, 2021). Similarly, external internships offer a great opportunity for students to have the first work experience that many companies demand when hiring recent graduates and to demonstrate to potential employers the preparation they have for possible future hiring (Di

Meglio et al., 2022, Urquía-Grande and Pérez-Estébanez, 2021; Wang and Lee, 2019) or to carry out entrepreneurship projects (Tusyanah et al., 2020).

Two competencies stipulated in the degree program that students must develop during their university education are key to professional success. We are referring to creativity and oral and written communication skills. These competencies are highly valued by employers who prioritize hiring creative individuals (Ortiz et al., 2016; Wesley et al., 2017) and those with high communication abilities (Suarta et al., 2017). Therefore, understanding to what extent universities are successfully helping students acquire these competencies during their education and feel satisfied when putting them into practice can provide valuable information to determine the effectiveness of the combination between classroom formulas and the completion of external internships. Similarly, firsthand knowledge of employers' perceptions (responsible tutors of the students in the companies) about the educational level of students in the analyzed competencies may be essential to consolidate the training model or adapt it if deemed necessary.

Likewise, organizing university teaching and practice in a way that helps to prevent any bias that could result in unequal education is a priority in university policies (David, 2017). Therefore, observing whether the training received and perceived regarding creativity and communication skills has the same impact on all students, regardless of their gender, can provide important considerations for educational planning.

2. External practices at the university

External internships are an indispensable complement to the education that students receive in the classroom and will help them to firsthand understand the professional and work world. The realization of external internships has a series of implications both for students and for companies that host interns, and the competencies demanded by companies and those acquired by students must coincide as much as possible. For students, it is an opportunity to improve their education, to be able to check if they are capable of applying the knowledge they have learned in the classroom to various subjects in practice, to develop professional competencies demanded in the workplace, and also to reinforce the acquisition of knowledge, professional skills, and attitudes. For employers, it will allow them to verify if the competencies learned by students in their higher education are the ones really required in job positions.

Most university degrees offer the possibility of carrying out external internships, either included in the curriculum (known as curricular internships), or also the possibility of carrying out voluntary internships (known as extracurricular internships). The purpose of external internships is for students to acquire, enhance, and develop certain transversal professional competencies, such as responsibility and commitment, autonomy, problem-solving, learning capacity, organization and planning skills, adaptability/flexibility, initiative, motivation, teamwork, interpersonal skills, oral and written communication skills, or creativity, among others. Among these competencies, creativity stands out as one of the most important in the business world, reflecting the ability of individuals to be creative when solving problems that arise in the work environment (Wesley et al., 2017).

Likewise, oral and written communication skills are essential for success in both company-client relationships and among employees, emphasizing the need for communication to be carried out in a professional, clear, and concise manner (Coffelt et al., 2019). Recent research analyzing the gap between the perceptions and expectations of the three actors involved in internships (employers-tutors in the company, academic tutor, and students) (Urquía-Grande and Pérez-Estébanez, 2021) highlights

that employers highly value oral and written communication skills of students on internships, while, on the contrary, they express the need to improve their creativity and cognitive skills. On the other hand, students highlight, among the knowledge and skills acquired in university, applicable to internships, the ability to work in a team, solidarity, oral competencies, and creativity. However, despite their perceived relevance, students express a very negative perception regarding the relationship between the transversal competencies learned in university and those demanded in the company, especially in the case of creativity.

In this regard, a factor that should be important when developing internships is the duration of them since it seems logical to think that the more hours of internships the students carry out, the greater the value they will give to the acquired competencies, as the process of competency learning will increase. An adequate duration contributes to increasing levels of interaction and integration and can have a positive effect on the performance of the functions assigned by the company to the students (Calero-López and Rodríguez-López, 2020). On the contrary, a time considered insufficient makes the students perceive that they are poorly prepared to perform the functions related to their degree when they have to integrate into a job position in the future. In this regard, it is suggested that this aspect could be improved by extending the duration of internships (Muñoz-García and González-Montegudo, 2020).

2.1. External practices at the University of Vigo

In the regulations of the University of Vigo (Uvigo, 2021), it is stated that external internships are a formative activity carried out by students, supervised by the university, that allows them to apply and complement the knowledge acquired during their academic training. For academic purposes, external internships can take two modalities: i) curricular internships, which are academic activities integrated into the curriculum as mandatory or elective. The treatment of these internships is like any other subject: they have several credits assigned and are graded by the academic tutor in the subject's transcript; ii) extracurricular internships, which have the same goals as curricular internships but are not included in the curriculum and are completely voluntary. Curricular internships will be reflected in the student's transcript, as well as in the European supplement to the degree, and extracurricular internships will also be recorded at the student's request.

Regarding the extracurricular internships that are the subject of this research work, the University of Vigo Foundation¹ (FUVI) is the entity that manages them, both concerning the companies and the students who wish to participate in this type of internship. FUVI promotes extracurricular internships among students and companies, highlighting their significant benefits for both groups (see Figure 1).

¹ Non-profit entity created in 1997 to promote actions in the field of employment, entrepreneurship and training. Fundación Universidade de Vigo | University of Vigo Foundation (<https://fundacionuvigo.es>)

Figure 1: *Extracurricular external practical advantages for companies and students.*

Source: Elaboration made from <https://fundacionuvigo.es>

FUVI manages extracurricular internships through a procedure that includes (Figure 2):

Figure 2: *Extracurricular practices management procedure by the FUVI.*

Source: Own elaboration based on <https://fundacionuvigo.es>

The University of Vigo has a regulation that includes the specific procedure governing extracurricular external internships, which regulates (Uvigo, 2021): the maximum and minimum duration, the procedure for assigning students to the company where the internships will take place, the procedure for assigning academic tutorship to the internships, the responsibilities in carrying out and approving the training project, the rules regarding the scholarships that will be received, the process for carrying out and submitting reports and, where appropriate, the final report of the internship, and the submission by the employer (responsible tutor in the company) and by the student of an evaluation report on the

internship carried out. These internship evaluation reports, which must be filled out by both employers and students at the end of the internships and submitted to the academic tutor, contain three types of data that both groups must fill out: i) personal data; ii) a set of general criteria on the evolution of the internships; iii) the assessment of a series of competencies acquired or developed during the internships.

2.2. The competencies acquired in the practices: creativity and communication skills

Creativity and its innovation aspect are currently considered a fundamental element in the selection processes of companies (Ortiz et al., 2016; Wesley et al., 2017), especially in the current socio-economic framework (Kümmel and Lindenberger, 2020; Cohen and Cromwell, 2020), so planning teaching in a way that students can develop their creative potential is an essential task in higher education institutions (Badger, 2019). Nowadays, companies and organizations are aware that, in the face of uncertainties that can determine their success, their employees' ability to be creative and innovative places them in a more advantageous position to progress and thrive in a rapidly changing economic environment (Khan and Mohiya, 2020).

Along with creativity, communication skills have been highlighted as essential for transmitting messages and knowledge (Klaus, 2010), becoming decisive for executives (Robles, 2012) and in business management, determining employee performance, business growth, and long-term profitability (Kalogiannidis, 2020) and business success (Masa'deh et al., 2019). Not possessing the necessary oral and written communication skills constitutes an important training deficiency and limitation that can result in a candidate's rejection despite their technical skills (Pauw et al., 2008). The relevance of both skills has been widely documented by recent research, concluding that the current competitive labor market and new management approaches require employees to possess both creative skills, especially those related to critical thinking and problem-solving, and particularly effective communication competencies (Baird and Parayitam, 2019; Suarta et al., 2017; McGunagle and Zizka, 2020). In this regard, it is noteworthy that there is a lack of synchronicity between the demands of the labor market and educational aspects, highlighting that oral and written communication skills in the university context do not receive the necessary attention, with ample room for improvement being detected (Grigorenko, 2019). This also happens in the case of creativity, observing its limited presence and development in the context of higher education, despite the widespread recognition of its relevance. This discrepancy is observed in the absence of this competency within the explicit objectives of higher education, coupled with universities' lack of preparation to create structures that foster students' creativity (Jahnke et al., 2020). This scenario is replicated in some degrees of the Spanish university, where it is detected that, although scores for non-technical competencies are quite positively valued, the two least scored were creativity and oral and written communication skills (Mareque and De Prada, 2018). The lack of formal training is not compensated by activities that students can develop outside the classroom, observing that very few students dedicate time to the practice of communication skills: less than 11% of students report practicing writing in their free time, while almost 60% report not reading in their leisure time (Mareque et al., 2019).

The absence of opportunities to promote and develop communication skills can also play an important role in activating or restricting students' creative potential. There is broad consensus in the literature regarding the important link between oral and written communication skills and creativity (Bowers et al., 2014; Trnka et al., 2016; Wang, 2012), emphasizing that greater practice of these skills results in an increase in creativity in students, a relationship that increases if more time is devoted to reading and writing (Wang, 2012). In the Spanish context, the leisure activity most related to creativity was, along with visual arts, and writing, highlighting the important link between the two (Mareque et al., 2019). Thus, the skills and activities that have been most related to creativity do not seem to receive

the necessary attention or be practiced enough, despite the conviction that creativity can be increased through communication skills (McVey, 2008), putting the necessary connection between education and the labor market at risk.

3. Communication skills, creativity, and gender

The relationship between gender and creativity has been the subject of numerous studies in recent years (Abdulla et al., 2022), and while a large majority of authors tend to show a lack of consistency that would confirm the existence of general-level differences (Baer and Kaufman, 2008), many others have found significant differences when making comparisons in various contexts and fields (Alvarez-Huerta et al., 2021). Therefore, studies are still necessary, especially in the field of higher education that can explain in which situations creativity may be affected by the student's gender since differences will depend on the type or aspect of creativity being measured (Charyton and Snelbecker, 2007). Regarding the case at hand, it is usually emphasized that women score better on verbal creativity tests (Abraham, 2016). Regarding communication skills, significant gender differences have also been found in favor of female students, who obtain better results in the dimensions of empathy, structure, verbal expression, and nonverbal expression (Graf et al., 2017). These differences are maintained in the formative aspect, where it is observed that female students show more positive and less negative attitudes toward learning communication skills than male students, which corroborates the conclusions of other authors (Cleland et al., 2005).

Considering the important impact of practices on the acquisition of creativity and communication skills, as we have mentioned, it is relevant to identify if differences between men and women can also be observed in this aspect. In this regard, recent research has highlighted that female university students tend to contact their practice supervisors more frequently and request more information about the practices than their male counterparts (Ho and Squires, 2022).

Based on the results of the described research, we propose the following research questions:

RQ1: Are there differences between the evaluations given by students and employers (supervisors in companies) regarding creativity competencies and oral and written communication skills during internships?

RQ2: Are there differences in the perception of the acquisition of creativity competencies and oral and written communication skills between male and female students, as perceived by both students and employers?

RQ3: Are there differences in the perception of the acquisition of creativity competencies and oral and written communication skills by both students and employers depending on the duration of the internships?

RQ4: Is there a relationship between creativity competencies and oral and written communication skills, as evaluated by both students and employers?

4. Objectives

The main objective of this study is to analyze the self-perception of students and the perception of employers (tutors responsible for the students in the companies) when students carry out their external internships regarding two of the transversal competencies that are developed in them, specifically, creativity and oral and written communication skills. The possible interaction between these two

competencies will also be studied. Finally, we will try to determine the existence of differences in the self-perception of students and in the evaluations of employers for both competencies based on the gender of the students and the duration of the internships. In this way, we aim to contribute new evidence on the assessment, interrelation, and differential factors of two of the transversal competencies most in demand by companies, creativity, and oral and written communication skills.

5. Methodology

The methodology used is based on a cross-sectional observational approach through a descriptive correlational design, where once reports with the assessment of acquired competencies during internships by both students and employers are received, the information is coded. When assessing competencies, various techniques can be used. Some techniques ask subjects to give a certain rating of specific competencies, while others focus on analyzing the behavior of individuals in their job position. Other techniques aim to assess competencies based on individual traits or characteristics (Gil, 2007). This study is based on the first technique, where both students and employers are asked to provide their perception of different competencies, including creativity and oral and written communication skills, which are the focus of this study.

5.1. Participants

The study population consists of all employers and students participating in extracurricular academic internships in the Degree in Business Administration and Management at the Ourense campus (Uvigo). A total of 638 internship records were analyzed, half of them filled out by the students and the other half by the employers (responsible tutors in the companies). In the case of students, the sample consisted of 204 women (64%) and 115 men (36%).

5.2. Instrument

As previously mentioned, the management of extracurricular external internships carried out by students at the University of Vigo is developed through a procedure that determines that, at the end of the internships, both the students and the tutor in the company must complete a report to evaluate a list of competencies supposedly developed in them. Among these competencies to be evaluated are creativity and oral and written communication skills. These competencies are measured through a Likert-type scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates "poor" and 5 "excellent". In addition, the instrument collects other informative data such as the gender of the students or the number of hours of duration of the internships, which mostly have a duration of 240 hours (average hours worked 266 hours). To corroborate the reliability of the measurement scale, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated, whose results showed an alpha coefficient of 0.7 for the student sample and 0.8 for the employer sample, which implies acceptable reliability in both cases (Sijtsma and Pfadt, 2021).

5.3. Analysis of data

Data analysis was performed using the statistical package SPSS 25.0. First, descriptive statistics are calculated to detail the basic characteristics of the data. Next, an analysis of means is performed using the Student's t-test. Finally, to establish the relationship between the scale variables, the Pearson correlation is calculated.

6. Results

6.1. Descriptive statistics and univariate analysis

In Table 1, it can be observed that, for the entire sample, both the self-perception given by the students and the perception of the employers is relatively high in both competencies, especially in communication skills ($\bar{x}=4.59$ employers and $\bar{x}=4.47$ students). However, it is worth noting the difference in the evaluation of creativity by the students ($\bar{x}=3.93$) and the employers ($\bar{x}=4.45$), with the students perceiving themselves as having lower creativity competencies.

The value of the median, both for students and employers and for both competencies, is 5, except for creativity rated by students, which is 4. Regarding the mode, the most repeated score by students and employers is 5, except for student creativity, which is 4. The standard deviation indicates that, in both cases, the evaluations given by the students have higher variability than those given by the employers.

Table 1. *Descriptive statistics.*

	Total sample						
	N	Min.	Máx.	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.
Employer communication skills	319	2	5	4,59	5,00	5	0,617
Employer creativity	319	1	5	4,45	5,00	5	0,698
Student communication skills	319	1	5	4,47	5,00	5	0,730
Student creativity	319	1	5	3,93	4,00	4	1,006

Source: Author's own work.

The results of the second research question regarding the existence of differences based on the gender of the students, concerning the level of creativity and oral and written communication skills attributed by employers and students, are shown in Table 2, where it is observed that there are no differences ($p\text{-value}>0.01$).

Table 2: *T-Student for the communication skills and creativity of students based on their gender.*

	Gender	N	t-Test				
			Media	S.D.	F	t	Sig.
Employer communication skills	Female	115	4,50	0,706	13,404	-1,916	0,057
	Male	204	4,64	0,557			
Employer creativity	Female	115	4,44	0,728	1,667	-0,152	0,879
	Male	204	4,46	0,683			
Student communication skills	Female	204	4,51	0,712	3,361	-1,188	0,236
	Male	115	4,41	0,760			
Student creativity	Female	204	3,98	0,949	5,281	-0,938	0,349
	Male	115	3,86	1,099			

Source: Author's own work.

Table 3 contains the results for the third research question regarding the relationship between the duration of the internships and the creativity and oral and written communication skills evaluated by both students and employers. It can be observed that the duration of the internships influences the self-perception of students regarding the development of their oral and written communication skills (p -value < 0.01) and their level of creativity (p -value < 0.05). No differences were found for employers in this regard (p -value > 0.05).

Table 3: *T-Student for the communication skills and creativity of the students depending on the duration of the practices.*

	Duration in hours	N	Mean	S.D.	t-Test		
					F	t	Sig.
Employer communication skills	<300 hours	242	4,57	0,608	0,313	-0,767	0,444
	>301 hours	77	4,64	0,647			
Employer creativity	<300 hours	242	4,45	0,699	0,013	-0,045	0,964
	>301 hours	77	4,45	0,699			
Student communication skills	<300 hours	242	4,41	0,780	22,041	-3,271	0,001**
	>301 hours	77	4,66	0,503			
Student creativity	<300 hours	242	3,87	1,000	0,185	-1,969	0,050*
	>301 hours	77	4,13	1,005			

* $p < 0,05$; ** $p < 0,01$

Source: Author's own work.

6.2. Multivariate analysis

To answer the last research question, the existence of a relationship between the creativity competencies and the oral and written communication skills assessed by both students and employers, Table 4 shows the results of the correlation matrix, where a positive and significant correlation (p -value < 0.01) between the two competencies studied is observed, although the scores given by the employer and the self-perception of the student are lower. It is noteworthy that employers rate the competencies studied more positively.

Table 4: *Correlation matrix.*

		Employer communication skills	Employer creativity	Student communication skills
Employer creativity	Correlation Coeff	,643**		
	Sig.	0,000		
Student's communication skills	Correlation Coeff	,363**	,240**	
	Sig.	0,000	0,000	
Students creativity	Correlation Coeff	,220**	,302**	,527**
	Sig.	0,000	0,000	0,000

** $p < 0,01$

Source: Author's own work.

7. Discussion and Conclusions

Regarding the main objective of this study, the high rating given by both groups on communication skills shows that both students and employers are highly satisfied with the level of competence acquired in the university setting and developed during internships, highlighting the synchrony between the training received and the communication skills required in the job market. However, this relationship is less effective in the case of creativity, confirming the need to improve its development to adapt to the demands of the real world (Urquía-Grande and Pérez-Estébanez, 2021; Wesley et al., 2017). This situation requires the involvement of higher education institutions, which must try to promote creativity through various actions, both through purely academic activities and extra-academic activities (Mareque et al., 2019). In this regard, it has been emphasized that creativity should not necessarily be conceived as an isolated subject but as an approach applicable to any content in the curriculum, giving teachers a fundamental role determined by their teaching style and didactic strategies (Castelló-Martínez, 2020). It is important to highlight that students have a more negative perception of their own competencies than employers, so the university institution should provide pedagogical formulas and actions aimed at helping students recognize their strengths and motivating them to improve.

A highly interesting result is the significant relationship found between the two competencies studied, communication skills and creativity, confirming the findings of previous studies (Bowers et al., 2014; Trnka et al., 2016) that highlight the important link between them, recommending an increase in tasks and activities related to oral and written communication skills (Mareque et al., 2019; Wang, 2012). The relationship between both competencies could suggest important synergies between them, so trying to integrate training actions that favor the acquisition of both skills together and complementarily could contribute to the development of the students' full communicative and creative potential.

Regarding the gender of the students, no differences were found, although the evaluation of women is higher, both in their self-perceptions and in the evaluations given by employers. In this sense, further research is needed regarding possible gender differences in the field of communication skills and creativity. Studies related to verbal creativity (Abraham, 2016) that give women higher scores could provide interesting implications for the relationship between creativity and communication skills according to gender. Similarly, the fact that women are more interested in obtaining information about internships and seeking advice may determine a greater realization of them, thereby favoring the development and assimilation of the skills under study (Ho and Squires, 2022).

Regarding the duration of the internships, we can highlight that the students perceive that the longer the internships, the greater the improvement in their competencies, both in creativity and in the development of communication skills. Previous studies also confirm this perception among students, both when they undertake national internships (Calero-López and Rodríguez-López, 2020; Muñoz-García and González-Monteaudo, 2020) and international ones (Di Pietro, 2022).

As highlighted, the complexity of the current job market determines the value of competencies such as communication skills and creativity that provide a great competitive advantage. Higher education institutions should not remain oblivious to these needs and should review whether undergraduate programs, especially in management, meet the demands of the business environment (Ritter et al., 2018). Similarly, universities must be involved in enhancing professional internships, ensuring adequate duration, carrying out sufficient informational sessions, and promoting the establishment of inter-institutional agreements, which will promote permanent hiring of students on internships (Anjum, 2020; Moss-Pech, 2021).

In conclusion, professional internships are presented as an ideal complement to university education in the two competencies under study, which show a significant relationship. This connection may be essential for proposing actions aimed at their practice and interaction in order to improve students' communication and creativity (McVey, 2008). In addition to the educational aspect, according to numerous authors (Khan and Mohiya, 2020; Martins and Terblanche, 2003), a favorable work environment is fundamental for creativity and innovation to develop. Therefore, transferring the implementation of a deliberately creative context, as is the case in the most innovative companies and organizations, to the university setting (Azeem et al., 2019), may be crucial to fully developing students' communicative and creative potential.

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